

Relationship between Head Nurses' Talent Management and their Nursing Staff Organizational Commitment

Rehab habashy el sayed aly¹, Elham Youssef Elhanafy²,
Mayada Hassan Saad Elzohairy³

¹(Infection Control Assistant Medical Affairs AL-Amaria Region Alexandria Health Directorate)

²(Professor of Nursing Administration Nursing Administration Department Faculty of Nursing, Damanshour University)

³(Lecturer of Nursing Administration, Faculty of Nursing, Damanshour University), Egypt

Corresponding author: Rehab Habashy El sayed Aly

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10219206>

Published Date: 29-November-2023

Abstract: Talented head nurses create differential value and make contributions to organizations. Talent management has been advocated as an important strategy to engage and retain their head nurses. Organizational commitment is considered to be one of the foremost important and crucial outcomes of the human resource strategies and the head nurses' commitment is seen as the key factor in achieving competitive performance. Aim of the Study: Investigate the relationship between head nurses' talent management and their nursing Staff organizational commitment at Alamrya Governmental Hospital. Research Design: A descriptive, correlational research design was utilized to conduct this study; design was conducted at Alamrya governmental Hospital, Alexandria Governorate affiliated to the Ministry of Health. Sampling: all staff nurses who was available at the time of data collection, were included in the study (N=278) and (N=17) head nurses. Tools: two tools were used in this study: Talent Management Questionnaire and Organization Commitment Questionnaire. Results: findings of this study illustrated that there is highly statistically significance between the levels of nurses' perception of organizational commitment overall dimensions and their levels of talent management Conclusion: illustrated that there were highly statistical significance correlations between all dimensions of talent management and all dimensions of organizational commitment Recommendation: Strategies and policies are required to develop the necessary vision to engage and retain talented nurses. Provide an effective compensation program to increase the commitment and retention of nurses.

Key Words: Talent management and organizational commitment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Talent management (TM) is the fundamental engine behind a health organization's success in today's competitive market. ⁽¹⁾ As a result, health organizations are vying to attract and keep talent to keep running and expanding. ⁽²⁾ Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development CIPD, ⁽⁴⁾ defined talent management as "the systematic attraction, identification, development, engagement, retention, and deployment of those head nurses who are of particular value to an organization". The key to successful retention and a requirement for a sustainable organization is providing the optimal head nurses' experience, and here is where talent management is crucial. So, talent managers are in charge of fostering the talent needed to meet their organizations' present and future needs. ⁽³⁾

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (352-360), Month: September - December 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Talent management is classified by Fapohunda,⁽⁵⁾ into four strategies: Talent attraction; is a specific recruitment technique that actively selects the highest caliber and most competent head nurses, Talent retention; is an effort in which the head nurses are encouraged to remain with the health care organization for a lifetime or maximum period, Learning and development; refers to educational activities within health care organizations designed to enhance the fulfilment and performance of head nurses learning and development, and finally Career management; is the process for enabling head nurses to better understanding and developing their career skills and interests. Each of these determinants must be designed to fit the strategic requirements of the healthcare organization and integrate.

Organizational commitment is one of the elements that guarantee the commitment of the head nurse with the quality of service and care, even in high-stress situations and work contexts with few human and organizational resources.⁽⁶⁾ Organizational commitment refers to the existence of a desire, a necessity, and an obligation to remain as a member of an organization.

Osemeké⁽⁷⁾ defined organizational commitment as "loyalty to the organization's ideals and aims, a sense of belonging, dependency, and a moral obligation to stay with the health care organization". Work-life quality has an impact on organizational commitment.

Meyer and Allen⁽⁸⁾ classified organizational commitment into three dimensions as following: affective commitment is head nurses' emotional attachment to their organization; continuance commitment is nurses' attachment to their head nurse based on the consequences of leaving; and normative commitment is head nurses' moral attachment to their organization; head nurses with a strong moral commitment have the conviction to serve the healthcare organization with a high degree of loyalty to the organization.

Through talent management strategies, healthcare managers can play a key role in improving overall human resource performance in healthcare organizations and overcoming all factors that lead to turnover, absenteeism, dissatisfaction, and leaving.⁽⁹⁾ The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between Head Nurses' Talent Management and their Nursing Staff Organizational Commitment. The findings of such a study can help healthcare administrators become more aware of talent management tactics at work and highlight a variety of ways that can help healthcare executives improve their practical skills in talent attraction and retention.⁽¹⁰⁾

Significance of study:

Human resources executives are frequently held liable for the successful execution of talent management programs, while it is the head nurses who really apply this method on a day-to-day basis.⁽¹¹⁾ Talent management creates a mutual commitment between talented head nurses and the organization by providing an optimal work environment, with a Talent positive impact on their performance.⁽¹²⁾ It can also be linked to organizational commitment (OC) and professional affiliations⁽¹³⁾ with more likelihood to achieve the goals of the organization.⁽¹⁴⁾ This result is consistent with Abazeed (2018)⁽¹⁵⁾ stated that TM has a significant direct and indirect effect on OC.

Aim of the Study:

This study aims to investigate the relationship between Head Nurses' Talent Management and their Nursing Staff Organizational Commitment.

Research Question:

What is the relationship between head nurses' talent management and their nursing staff organizational commitment at alamrya governmental hospital?

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

I- Materials

Research design:

Adescriptive correlational research design was utilized to conduct this study.

Setting of the study: the study was conducted in Alamrya General Hospital, Alexandria Governorate affiliated to the Ministry of Health and population with a bed capacity of 123 beds and consists of 17 units as follows; ICU, Intermediate Care Unit, (2) Units NICU, Emergency Department, Outpatient, (3) Dialysis Units, Operating Rooms, Inpatient Male Unit, Inpatient Female Unit, Isolation, Orthopedics, Pediatric, Central Sterilization and Supply Department, and Obstetrics and Gynecology unit.

Subjects:

Two groups of subjects were included in this study:

- a) All head nurses who are working in the previously mentioned settings and who was available at the time of data collection, was included in the study (N=17).
- b) All staff nurses who are working in the previously mentioned settings and who was available at the time of data collection, was included in the study (N=278).

Tools of the study:

The following two tools were used in this study:

Tool (I): Talent Management Questionnaire

The talent Management Questionnaire was developed by Lyria (2013)⁽¹⁶⁾ it consists of 35 items and is classified into four components as follow: talent attraction (8-items); talent retention (9-items); learning and development (8-items); and finally, career management (10-items).

The responses were measured on five points Likert scale and they are ranged from (5) strongly agree to (1) strongly disagree. The overall score level ranged from (35 -175), the low level of talent management ranged from (35 -82), the moderate level ranged from (82-128) and the high level ranged from (128-175).

Tool (II): Organization Commitment Questionnaire

Organization Commitment Questionnaire was developed by Meyer and Allen (1997)⁽¹⁷⁾ it consists of 24 items classified into three dimensions as follow: affective commitment (8-items); continuance commitment (8-items); and normative commitment (8-items).

The responses were measured on five points Likert scale and they are ranged from (5) strongly agree to (1) strongly disagree. The overall score level ranged from (24 -120), the low level of Organization Commitment ranged from (24 - 56), the moderate level ranged from (57- 88) and the high level ranged from (89-120).

In addition, the demographic questionnaire was developed by the researcher for the two study groups: age, gender, marital status, educational qualifications, and years of experience in the nursing and nursing units.

II- Methods

1. An official permission was obtained from the Dean Faculty of Nursing, Damanhour University and the responsible authorities of the study settings after explanation the purpose of the study.
2. The two tools were translated into Arabic and tested for their content validity and translated by five experts in the field of the study. Accordingly, the necessary modifications were done. It has been modified in Affective Commitment Scale to talk about the advantages of the hospital with others instead of speaking in general about the hospital in order to preserve the ethics of the profession.

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (352-360), Month: September - December 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

3. The two tools were tested for their reliability using chi square test, it was found that a highly statistically significance between the levels of staff nurses' perception of overall dimensions of organizational commitment and their levels of talent management.
4. A pilot study for the questionnaires were carried out on (10%) of the total sample size; head nurses (2) and nurses (28); who were not included in the study sample; to check and to ensure the clarity and feasibility of the tool and to identify obstacles and problems that may be encountered during data collection. modifications were done.
5. Data was collected from the identified subjects, by the researcher through hand-delivered questionnaire at their working setting after explaining the aim of the study. Every nurse took about (15) to (20) minutes to fill the two tools. The data collection took about four months from 1st of July to 30th of October, twenty-twenty-one, where two units were interviewed weekly.

Ethical considerations:

- The research approval was obtained from the ethical committee at the faculty of Nursing-Damanhour University, prior to the start of the study.
- An informed written consent was obtained from the study subject after explanation of the aim of the study.
- Privacy, confidentiality and right to refuse to participate or withdraw from the study was assured during the study.
- Anonymity regarding data collected was maintained.

III. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

1. The collected data was coded and entered in a special format to be suitable for computer feeding. Following data entry, checking and verification process were carried out in order to avoid any errors.
2. Data was analyzed using the statistical package for social science SPSS (version 20).
3. The following statistical analysis measures were used:
 - a. Descriptive statistical measures, which included numbers, percentages, and averages (Minimum, Maximum, Arithmetic mean (X), and Standard Deviation (SD).
 - b. Statistical analysis tests, which included: Chi square (X²), T test and ANOVA test.

IV. RESULTS

Table (1): Distribution of the studied subjects according to their demographic characteristic at Alamrya Government Hospital.

Table (1) shows the demographic characteristics of the subjects, considering to working unit, staff nurses were presented in the three different units (medical–surgical – ICU) equally, the percentage was (33.1%, 32% and 34.9%), repressively. Where, most of the head nurses working in the ICU represented (41.2%), followed by 35.3% in the medical unit and 23.5% in the surgical unit. According to age, above two-quarters of staff nurses (67.6%) were between 20 and less than 30 years old, the mean age was 28.4 and SD was ± 5.76 , while nearly half of the head nurses (47.1%) were between 30 and less than 40 years old, the mean age was 36.8 and SD was ± 6.18 . Regarding gender, all head nurses were female, while 41.7% of the staff nurses were male in comparison to (58.3%) were female. According to marital status, the majority of both groups were married, represented by 62.6% of the staff nurses in comparison to (82.4%) of the head nurses.

Regarding educational qualification, it was found that all of the head nurses had a Bachelor of Science in Nursing, in comparison, 48.9% of the staff nurses had a Bachelor of Science in Nursing, 41.7% had a Diploma from Technical Health Institute and only 9.4% had a Diploma of Secondary Technical Nursing School. Concerning years of nursing experience, nearly half of the staff nurses (48.6%) had experienced between one year and less than 5 years, although the majority of the head nurses (82.4%) had more than 10 years of nursing experience. Regarding unit experience, more than two-quarters of the staff nurses (67.6%) had experienced less than 1-year. whereas, then half of the head nurses (52.9%) had more than 10 years of nursing experience.

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (352-360), Month: September - December 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Table (1): Distribution of the studied subjects according to their demographic characteristic at Alamrya Government Hospital. (n= 295)

Demographic characteristics	Staff nurses (N= 278)		Head nurses (N=17)		Total (N= 295)	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Working Unit						
Medical	92	33.1	6	35.3	98	33.2
Surgical	89	32	4	23.5	93	31.5
ICU	97	34.9	7	41.2	104	35.3
Age (years)						
20 -	188	67.6	2	11.8	190	64.4
30 -	72	25.9	8	47.1	80	27.1
40 +	18	6.5	7	41.2	25	8.5
Min-Max 21– 48			Min-Max 25 – 48 Mean		Min-Max 21 – 48 Mean ±SD	
Mean ±SD 28.4± 5.762			±SD 36.8± 6.187		28.9±6.097	
Gender						
Male	116	41.7	-	-	116	39.3
Female	162	58.3	17	100	179	60.7
Marital status						
Single	104	37.4	3	17.6	107	36.3
Married	174	62.6	14	82.4	188	63.7
Educational qualifications						
Diploma of Secondary Technical Nursing School	26	9.4	-	-	26	8.8
Diploma of Technical Health Institute	116	41.7	-	-	116	39.3
Bachelor of Science in Nursing	136	48.9	17	100	153	51.9
Years of nursing experience						
1-	135	48.6	1	5.9	136	46.1
5-	80	28.7	2	11.8	82	27.8
10 +	63	22.7	14	82.4	77	26.1
Min-Max 1 – 32			Min-Max 4 – 25		Min-Max 1 – 32 Mean ±SD	
Mean ±SD 6.6± 5.762			Mean ±SD15.4±6.245		7.2±6.127	
Years of unit experience						
1-	188	67.6	5	29.5	193	65.4
5-	54	19.5	3	17.6	57	19.3
10 +	36	12.9	9	52.9	45	15.3
Min-Max 1 – 28			Min-Max 2 – 23		Min-Max 1 – 28 Mean ±SD	
Mean ±SD 4.8± 4.691			Mean ±SD 9.5±5.680		5.1±4.864	

Table (2): The relationship between staff nurses and head nurses according to their perceptions of talent management at Alamrya Government Hospital.

Table (2) presented the differences between staff nurses and head nurses according to their perceptions of talent management, there was no significant difference between head nurses and staff nurses as the following: talent attraction, the mean score of the nurses was 28.1 ± 6.135 , and the mean score of the head nurses were 29.5 ± 6.929 , $p = 0.344$; talent retention, the mean score of the staff nurses was 31.8 ± 6.789 . and the mean score of the head nurses was 28.2 ± 8.94 $p = 0.127$; in learning and development, the mean score of the staff nurses was 29 ± 6.515 , and the mean score of the head nurses

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (352-360), Month: September - December 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

was 27.1 ± 8.271 , $p=0.384$; and finally, career management, the mean score of the nurses was 35.5 ± 8.133 , and the mean score of the head nurses was 33.4 ± 9.207 , $p = 0.305$.

Table (2): The relationship between staff nurses and head nurses according to their perceptions of talent management, at Alamrya Government Hospital. (n= 295).

Talent management dimensions	Job Position				T	P
	Nurses (N=278)		Head nurses (N=17)			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Talent attraction	28.1	6.135	29.5	6.929	0.948	0.344
Talent retention	31.8	6.789	28.2	8.943	1.604	0.127
Learning and development	29	6.515	27.1	8.271	0.894	0.384
Career management	35.5	8.133	33.4	9.207	1.028	0.305
Total talent management	123.7	24.144	116.5	33.104	1.160	0.247

T=Independent samples t- test

The relationship between nurses and head nurses according to their organizational commitment at Alamrya Government Hospital.

Table (3) shows that there was no significant difference between the head nurses and staff nurses regarding organizational commitment as follows: affective commitment, the mean score of the staff nurses was 28.1 ± 6.257 and the mean score of the head nurses was 28.2 ± 6.220 , $p=0.930$; continuance commitment, the mean score of the nurses was 27.5 ± 6.259 and the mean score of the head nurses was 27.5 ± 6.196 , $p=0.976$; and normative commitment, the mean score of the nurses was 27.8 ± 6.802 and the mean score of the head nurses was 28.6 ± 6.403 , $p = 0.633$.

Table (3): The relationship between nurses and head nurses according to their organizational commitment at Alamrya Government Hospital. (n= 295).

Organization commitment dimensions	Job Position				T	P
	Nurses (N=278)		Head nurses (N=17)			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Affective commitment	28.1	6.257	28.2	6.220	0.088	0.930
Continuance commitment	27.5	6.259	27.5	6.196	0.030	0.976
Normative commitment	27.8	6.802	28.6	6.403	0.477	0.633
Total organization commitment	83.5	17.445	84.4	17.063	0.207	0.836

T=Independent samples t- test

*P value (significant) ≤ 0.05

Table (4): Correlation matrix between head nurses' talent management and their nursing staff organizational commitment at Alamrya Government Hospital.

Table 4 illustrated that there were highly statistically significant correlations between all dimensions of talent management and all dimensions of organizational commitment, where ($p=0.000$).

Table (4): Correlation matrix between head nurses' talent management and their nursing staff organizational commitment at Alamrya Government Hospital.

		Talent attraction (1)	Talent retention (2)	Learning and development (3)	Career management (4)	Total Talent Management (5)	Affective commitment (6)	Continuance commitment (7)	Normative commitment (8)	Total Organization Commitment (9)
Talent attraction (1)	r	1	0.529	0.547	0.487	0.66	0.402	0.465	0.474	0.496
	P (2-tailed)		0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000*
Talent retention (2)	r		1	0.82	0.806	0.916	0.648	0.635	0.606	0.696
	P (2-tailed)			0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000*
Learning and development (3)	r			1	0.85	0.93	0.617	0.636	0.669	0.71
	P (2-tailed)				0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000*
Career management (4)	r				1	0.921	0.645	0.664	0.676	0.733
	P (2-tailed)					0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000*
Total talent management (5)	r					1	0.661	0.689	0.695	0.755
	P (2-tailed)						0.000**	0.000**	0.000**	0.000*
Affective commitment (6)	r						1	0.766	0.661	0.891
	P (2-tailed)							0.000**	0.000**	0.000*
Continuance commitment (7)	r							1	0.747	0.925
	P (2-tailed)								0.000**	0.000*
Normative commitment (8)	r								1	0.895
	P (2-tailed)									0.000*
Total organization commitment (9)	r									1
	P (2-tailed)									

r=Pearson Correlation *P value at level ≤ 0.05 (statistically significant)

**P value (highly significant) ≤ 0.01 Interpretation of r:

Weak (0.1-0.24) Intermediate (0.25-0.7) Strong (0.75-0.99) Perfect (1)

V. DISCUSSION

TM has been a critical issue for many health organizations and a challenging situation for human resource managers. In recent years, studies on TM have increased ⁽¹⁸⁻¹⁹⁾

Concerning the relationship between the study subjects' perception of TM and their OC, the findings of this study illustrated that there is high statistical significance between the levels of nurses' perception of OC overall dimensions and their levels of talent management. This result is consistent with Abazeed (2018) ⁽¹⁵⁾ stated that TM has a significant direct and indirect effect on OC. Consequently, employee management dimensions have significantly mediated the effect of TM on OC.

Regarding the relationship between staff nurses and head nurses according to their perceptions of talent management, at Alamrya General Hospital. The results of this study showed that there is no difference between staff nurses and head nurses according to their perceptions of talent management. The result showed that the majority of the study subjects got a moderate perception of talent management.

The present study distribution of the subjects according to their perceptions of organization commitment dimensions that

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (352-360), Month: September - December 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

above half had moderate level of organization commitment, more than third had high level of organization commitment. That nearly half of the study subjects represented had moderate perception regarding the affective commitment.

Finally, the correlation matrix between head nurses' and their nursing staff OC at Alamrya General Hospital. Were highly statistical significance correlations between all dimensions of TM and all dimensions of OC. This result is consistent with Atalla and Farghally (2019) ⁽²⁰⁾ who found the same result was highly statistical significance with a moderate correlation between the overall mean score of nurses' perceptions of TM and the overall mean score of OC.

VI. CONCLUSION

The present study found that there were highly statistical significance correlations between talent management and organizational commitment across all dimensions. The study also revealed a significant correlation between talent management and educational qualifications, Similarly, there was a significant correlation between organizational commitment and educational qualifications.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the current study, the following recommendation can be suggested:

Healthcare organizations:

1. To attract experienced and qualified nurses, healthcare organizations should implement a talent search matrix that takes into account both potential and performance during the selection process.
2. Healthcare organizations should offer job security, improved financial rewards, and the best possible healthcare benefits to its nurses.

Head nurses should:

- Establish an effective performance appraisal policy that help in the development and improvement of nurse's performance.
- Encouraging staff nurses to pursue further education is crucial for enhancing their professional status.
- Provide supportive work condition through availability of adequate staff and resources to decrease workload and provide high quality care.
- Encourage teamwork through building team activities and communicate effectively and openly.

Nurses' staff should:

Future/Further studies should be conducted:

- Influence of Talent Management on Organizational Growth
- Organizational Commitment and Organizational Sustainability

REFERENCES

- [1] Mensah J. Talent management and employee outcomes: A psychological contract fulfilment perspective. Public Organization Review. 2019;19(3):325-44.
- [2] Elhanafy E, El Hessewi M. Effect of Talent Management Training Program on Head Nurses Leadership Effectiveness. Egyptian Journal of Health Care. 2021;12(4):351-61.
- [3] Singh R. Talent management literature review. Feedforward: Journal of Human Resource. 2021;1(1):43-8.
- [4] CIPD. Talent management. Understand the changing context and benefits of talent management, and the key features of a talent management strategy. . CIPD; 2020 .Available from: <https://www.cipdcouk/knowledge/strategy/>resourcing/talentfactsheet>.
- [5] Fapohunda T. Increasing organizational effectiveness through better talent management. Research Journal of Human Resource. 2014;2(4):1-14.

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (352-360), Month: September - December 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [6] Aiken L, Sermeus W, Van den Heede K, Sloane DM, Busse R, McKee M, et al. Patient safety, satisfaction, and quality of hospital care: cross sectional surveys of nurses and patients in 12 countries in Europe and the United States. *BMJ*. 2012;344.
- [7] Osemeke M. Identification of Determinants of Organizational Commitment and Employee Job Satisfaction. *African Research Review*. 2016;10(2):81-8.
- [8] Meyer J, Allen N. *TCM employee commitment survey academic users guide 2004*. London, Ontario, Canada: The University of Western Ontario; 2004.
- [9] Stahl G. *Global talent management: How leading multinationals build and sustain their talent pipeline*. Australia University: Institute for International Business; 2007.
- [10] Elhaddad S, Safan S, Elshall S. Nurses' Perception toward Talent Management and its Relationship to their Work Engagement and Retention. *Menoufia Nursing Journal*. 2020;5(2):25-38.
- [11] Abdrabou H, Ghonem N. Talent management training program and its effect on leadership effectiveness among nurse managers. *Egypt J Health Care*. 2020;11(3): 221-37
- [12] Berger L, Berger D. *The talent management handbook*. New York: McGraw-Hill 2004.
- [13] Rajabipoor M, Dehghani M. The relationship between Islamic work ethic and organizational commitment and job satisfaction of nurses. *Journal of bioethics*. 2013;2(3):49-92.
- [14] Karami A, Farokhzadian J, Foroughameri G. Nurses' professional competency and organizational commitment: Is it important for human resource management? *PLoS One*. 2017;12(11):11-26.
- [15] Abazeed RAM. The impact of talent management on organizational commitment of the employees of telecommunication companies in Jordan: the mediating role of employee work engagement. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*. 2018;8(4):153-62.
- [16] Lyria K. Role of talent management on organizational performance in companies listed in Nairobi securities exchange in Kenya. *Int J Humanities Soc Sci*. 2013;3(21):285-90.
- [17] Meyer J, Allen N. *Commitment in the workplace: Theory, Research and Application*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage publication; 1997. <https://sk.sagepub.com/books/download/commitment-in-the-workplace/n2.pdf>
- [18] Gallardo-Gallardo E, Thunnissen M. Standing on the shoulders of giants? A critical review of empirical talent management research. *Employee Relations*. 2016;38(1):31-56.
- [19] Thunnissen M, Boselie P, Fruytier B. Talent management and the relevance of context: Towards a pluralistic approach. *Human Resource Management Review*. 2013;23(4):326-36.
- [20] Atalla A, Farghally S. Emotional Intelligence Skills of Academic Nursing Faculty Members and the Presence of Uncivil Workplace Behaviors. *IOSR Journal of Nursing and Health Science (IOSR-JNHS)*. 2019;8(1):1-7.